

Technologies for learning in dark times

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Criticism on social media of a communicator who pointed out that after-dinner chats are a positive consequence of power outages has been labelled as an attempt to justify perceptions of government inaction.

It is clear that thousands of Ecuadorians must use their time creatively when blackouts occur. Manual tasks, reading or urban travel may occupy the hours, but tools that depend on electricity condition daily activities.

In many schools, they bring back the exhibitions supported by physical posters, they hold classes on tape, they return to libraries and do collective readings in the classrooms. Thus, the search for knowledge continues on the basis of traditional technologies.

The intention to look at the good in the crises clashes with mediatised and highly digitalised societies that give way to discussions about people's digital rights, where efforts are made to guarantee minimum conditions of respect for human beings.

From published information and expert testimonies, it is known that the problem of water shortages in Ecuador will last for years, and that the country is not in a position to obtain alternative energy sources in the short term. So how to organise the teaching and learning processes to make effective use of artificial light, how to provide for the rights to education and freedom of expression?

There will be transition periods where we will have to live with limited resources until we have permanent energy flows, especially non-polluting ones. Today the expectation is to reach December with fewer blackouts to maintain trade and jobs, but are Ecuadorians prepared to face the crisis of 2025?